

Figure 1. Front view showing bilateral and axial exophthalmos.

Figure 2. Exophthalmos in tangential view.

found polyclonal inflammatory infiltration and noncaseating granuloma.

The diagnosis of sarcoidosis was retained in view of the above-mentioned clinical data, especially the typical hilar adenopathy and the microscopic demonstration of noncaseating granuloma. The patient was put on oral corticosteroids, prednisone at a dosage of 1 mg/kg/day, and oral potassium supplementation. The evolution was marked by a clinical improvement with a regression of the exophthalmia and disappearance of lymphadenopathies.

Discussion

Sarcoidosis is an inflammatory disease of unknown cause that affects one or more organs but most commonly affected are the lungs, hilar and paratracheal lymph nodes, the skin, and the eyes [1]. The histopathologic hallmark of the disease is noncaseating granulomas. It is usually presenting in adults in their third through fifth decades [2–3].

Ophthalmological involvement in sarcoidosis (30% of sarcoidosis) may be characterized by granulomatous inflammation which can affect any part of the eye and its adnexa [4]. It is mainly represented by granulomatous anterior uveitis and intermediate uveitis. Palphalic sarcoids, lacrimal gland involvement, conjunctival nodules, posterior uveitis, and optic nerve involvement are also common.

Orbital disease in sarcoidosis is rare, it may be the initial manifestation of patients with sarcoidosis, and may cause severe visual impairment. The isolated orbital disease is uncommon but it is possible and generally limited to the lacrimal gland [2]. When it occurs in this context, it is usually unilateral and is the initial symptom. It can be bilateral—as in our case—only in rare cases [3,5–8].

Exophthalmos can be seen in various circumstances. It is confirmed by an exophthalmometry or the calculation of the oculo-orbital index on imagery [9]. Even in the absence of evocative ophthalmological involvement, sarcoidosis may be a part of exophthalmos causes, after ruling out the main causes which include: Graves' disease, carotid-cavernous fistula, tumor, and infectious causes.

The morphological exploration of exophthalmia is essentially based on CT scan and magnetic resonance imaging, ruling out a possible orbital tumor. Color

Doppler ultrasound is used to study the expansive processes, as well as the circulatory velocities in the vessels of the optic nerve head. In case of suspicion of inflammatory or tumoral pathology, the histological study makes it possible to affirm it by means of biopsies.

In our case, orbital/brain CT scan and MRI eliminated an intracranial tumor, the normal thyroid function excluded Graves' disease. The absence of inflammatory syndrome, the negative procalcitonin, and the good response to prednisone ruled out the hypothesis of infectious causes.

The results of a histological study of minor salivary glands biopsy, the elevated ACE level, the hypercalciuria, and typical hilar adenopathy were strong arguments to conclude that the presence of sarcoid granulomas in the retro-orbital tissues produced the patient's exophthalmos.

Visual prognosis of ocular sarcoidosis may vary depending upon severity and chronicity of eye inflammation. When orbital inflammation occurs, the treatment is based on oral corticosteroids and/or immunosuppressive agents. Systemic corticosteroids are rapidly effective. A high dose (1–1.5 mg/kg/day) of prednisone should be used for a limited duration to avoid side effects and tapered gradually to avoid relapse. Systemic immunosuppressive agents are indicated in patients who are corticosteroid-dependent or -intolerant [4].

Conclusion

Ocular involvement in sarcoidosis is an integral part of extra-thoracic locations. Sarcoidosis can involve almost any structure within or around the eye. Granulomatous infiltration of the orbital tissue during sarcoidosis remains very rare and exceptionally reported. Clinicians need to be aware of atypical ocular manifestations of sarcoidosis in order to make the diagnosis quickly and start corticosteroid therapy to avoid irreversible complications especially blindness.

Acknowledgement

None.

List of abbreviations

ACE	Angiotensin-converting enzyme
ALAT	Alanine Aminotransferase
ASAT	Aspartate Aminotransferase

Consent for publication

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's next of kin for publication of this case report and the accompanying images to publish this case.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval is not required at our institution for publishing a case report in a medical journal.

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Summary of the case

Patient (gender, age)	1	Male, 55-year-old
Final Diagnosis	2	Systemic sarcoidosis
Symptoms	3	Exophthalmos
Medications	4	Corticosteroid
Clinical Procedure	5	Prednisone: 1 mg/kg/day
Specialty	6	Internal Medicine/Ophthalmology